

TENDENCIES OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN UZBEKISTAN

Nurimova Ayzada Razatdinovna

Student at the Faculty of Foreign Languages, English Language and Literature, Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12743302>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 7th July 2024

Accepted: 8th July 2024

Published: 15th July 2024

KEYWORDS

Higher education, English, language, learning, method, level, CEFR, PISA, PIRLS.

ABSTRACT

English is one of the most important international languages. Learning this language is practiced in almost all state higher education systems. This article discusses the specifics, trends, directions, reforms and decisions in the teaching of English in the higher education system of Uzbekistan.

Higher education, English, language, learning, method, level, CEFR, PISA, PIRLS.

INTRODUCTION

These days, most people speak more than one languages. Of course, the first of these languages is their mother tongue, and many linguists believe that special conditions should be created not only for the foreign language being studied, but also for mastering the mother tongue. It should be noted that as a result of reforms in the study of foreign languages, the younger generation, from preschool to higher education, is simultaneously learning the native language and a foreign language.

With the help of existing research methods in linguistics, it is easier to study languages by comparing genetically related and non-genetically related language families, which have a high level and experience in international and interethnic communication. is a scientifically proven fact [3].

Textbooks, curricula and manuals created today to radically introduce the field of education in our country into foreign languages are a practical proof of these goals. Therefore, only a student who knows his language and culture well can learn other languages with love. Learning a foreign language requires similar special training. The question is - what is the need us for a foreign language?

Through the study of foreign languages, we have the opportunity to get acquainted with the intellectual potential of young people around the world, to exchange views with them, to analyze the process in depth and compare our achievements and shortcomings with theirs. Striving to learn foreign languages, following the proverb "A man who knows the language knows" is inherited from our great ancestors, such as Farobi, who knew many languages, and Kashgari, who was widely observed in the comparative study of several languages.

In addition, Abdullah Avloni's 1913 article "Four Languages, Not Two" published in the magazine "Oyna" explains in detail the need to learn a language in order to keep pace with the world. Our great ancestors are known and recognized all over the world for their innovations in science, for their ability to convey their unique works to other peoples in their own

language. Central Asian science, culture and enlightenment are respected. At the heart of all this, as we have repeatedly said, is language skills [4].

METHODS

It can be explained that the demand of today's youth is to learn foreign languages: to communicate directly with the countries of the world, to express their independent opinion in a fluent and understandable way in public, to make Uzbekistan a special place in the world community. The study of international languages is also an important issue in order to ensure and strengthen its role.

However, in addition to listing the advantages of language learning that only serve the good, it should be noted that such concepts as the state language, national language, mother tongue should always be in the first place for all of us. Just as every independent country has its own state language, the Uzbek language is a symbol of the independence of the Uzbek state. Learning another language should not lead to the conclusion that restricting the use of one's own language. Language is a symbol of the state, a mirror of the nation. It is the human duty of every nation to enrich its language, to polish it, to expand its scope, in a word, to pass it on to the next generation in an improved way [3].

The use of additional resources in teaching foreign languages to students, to further increase the interest and attitude of students to foreign languages through auxiliary teaching aids, to conduct each lesson in an interactive, ie active-student way, to add to them after classes teaching and the use of traditional methods in this process. In the process of lessons organized using innovative technologies, students increase their interest in foreign languages and improve their skills of independent creative work. The etymology of the term "innovative technology" in the scientific literature means "innovation", and "technology" as a linguodidactic concept, "an effort to achieve educational goals with less time, effort and money." a set of rational methods of scientific organization of the movement. The use of Case, Zigzag, Cluster, Brainstorming, Cinquain, Method, Project, Mind Mapping as specific methods of pedagogical technology in traditional pedagogy has yielded very good results.

RESULTS

Below we talk about new developing pedagogies.

1) Artificial intelligence in education. The term "artificial intelligence" (AI) is used to describe computer systems. Artificial intelligence education systems are rapidly entering schools, colleges and universities. Apps designed for students include smart learning systems, dialogue-based learning systems, research-based learning environments, automated writing assessment, and conversation agents. Although programs designed for teachers are less developed, they are a program that helps teachers improve their knowledge. It should be noted that the abilities of students and teachers, such as critical thinking, creativity, communication and collaboration, should be taken into account. It would be great if teachers, researchers, and other stakeholders could work together to develop both artificial intelligence applications and teaching and learning methods [5].

2) Learning through open data. More than 250 national, local and city governments and global organizations share, create and use information with each other. These organizations seek to see the information used by the public, and many advanced services provide resources for the study of open data. Subsequent initiatives led them to innovative education. Well, the question arises

- What does open data offer as material? What is its role in learning and teaching? The key factor is authenticity. Shared data is the result of real processes taking place within large organizations. The information that is often used in professional work has a real impact on our lives and the world around us. The second factor is the importance of this information in building the capacity of students. This can be a very strong psychological effect. Students will be able to compare what is happening in their cities, villages, and perhaps in their classrooms with what is happening near and far. In the process, they may also identify problems and

bring them to the attention of the local community or society as a whole. In one example, high school students in Italy were awarded for construction projects in the process of studying information on state funding. It is clear that open data connects students, and as a result of information literacy, transparency, and evidence-based action, social movements for greater motivation have emerged [6].

3) Dealing with information use ethics. The use of digital technology in growing education is accompanied by a constant increase in ethical questions. The ethical issues here are a lot of information, for example, who owns it, how to interpret the information, how to protect the privacy of students and professors? There have also been cases of criticizing people they are unaware of. Maybe it's just a matter of time. To prevent such problems, develop a policy on data ethics in educational institutions, obtain consent from students to use the data, analyze any information in their interaction, get acquainted with their views on the education management system, creating an effective teaching system, as well as student and staff support issues should also be considered. There are currently no official classes. To do this, teachers must create opportunities for students. In today's digital world, the exchange of information between institutes and universities increases their effectiveness.

DISCUSSION

The level of English teachers' knowledge of their subject is planned to be assessed jointly with the Swedish company Education first. The result of this exam will comply with the international CEFR system. It is planned to develop a specific program for improving the qualifications of English language teachers. With the help of this program, the strengths and weaknesses of English teachers will be studied and, based on the results of the conclusion, a program of special training courses will be created to improve the qualifications of teachers. Until today, there was no system for an impartial assessment of the knowledge of teachers, and this innovation is being introduced for the first time. The resolutions and decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted in 2018 played a fundamental role in improving the system of public education. In the field of modernization of the content of education, it is planned to radically change the content of general secondary education to create a competency-based learning model aimed at learning, first of all, foreign languages that are necessary in the future for mastering professions that are in demand within the framework of the innovative economy being created based on new educational standards, programs, textbooks and teaching materials. It is planned to create specialized classes and schools, with an emphasis on in-depth study of foreign languages, and ensure the participation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international programs and studies to assess the level of knowledge of students (PISA, TIMSS and PIRLS).

In 2003, in accordance with the Decree of the head of state "On improving the system of advanced training and internships for promising young teachers and scientific personnel", the Istedod Foundation of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established to organize advanced training, internships and study scholarship holders abroad, to attract on a permanent basis foreign specialists to the educational process in higher educational institutions. In pursuance of the decree of the head of state "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages," the foundation launched a three-stage educational project to improve the skills of English language teachers at all levels of education. Together with the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education, the Tashkent office of the British Council, the Republican Language Center and the Uzbek State University of World Languages, a number of programs have been developed. In accordance with them, about 90 teachers of English have successfully completed advanced training courses at the London Metropolitan University and the Norwich Institute of Language Education. Starting from the 2013/2014 academic year in Uzbekistan, in higher educational institutions in certain special subjects, especially in technical and international specialties, classes are conducted in foreign languages.

The state actively supports and motivates young people to learn foreign languages. Applicants who have certificates from the leading international examination systems (TOEFL, IELTS, CEFR, SAT General, SAT Subject and others), the maximum number of points in the relevant subjects are exempted from tests in these subjects. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further expand the participation of industries and sectors of the economy in improving the quality of training of specialists with higher education", starting from the 2017/2018 academic year, each higher educational institution conducts phased training in specialty disciplines in English in at least 2 th academic groups in all courses, targeted training of faculty for teaching in English [2]. Their corresponding training abroad was organized, as well as foreign specialists were involved in conducting training sessions. Training has been established on the basis of modern educational literature used today in higher educational institutions of developed countries. Internships for promising scientific and pedagogical personnel, primarily teachers of higher educational institutions for the training of personnel in engineering, technical and architectural areas of education, are carried out in developed countries, in particular, in South Korea, Japan and Germany, at 2-3 monthly courses aimed at for the development of new knowledge in the specialty.

The concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 is focused on knowledge and active study of foreign languages. By 2030, its targets plan to achieve 100 percent English language proficiency by English teachers corresponding to the C1-CEFR level of the European Union requirements by attaching professors of foreign languages departments of universities and 100 percent English proficiency results of graduates of general education institutions with knowledge of English who have mastered English language at level B1-CEFR requirements of the European Union [1].

References

1. "The concept of development of the system of public education of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" (Appendix N 1 to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 N UP-5712).
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 20, 2017 No. PP-2909 "On measures for the further development of the higher education system".
3. J. Jalolov, "Methods of teaching foreign languages", Tashkent-2012, pp. 99-100.
4. "Innovative Peadgogy 2020" magazine.
5. <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2019/08/26/> For text see https://polpred.com/?ns=1&ns_id=3100509
6. www.ziyonet.uz